

SHORTAGES IN A WORLD OF ABUNDANCE

Indonesia, Water Crises and Social-Environmental Injustice

Prathiwi Putri, a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellow at the University of Kassel. The project leading to this publication has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101029193. This brief has appeared in German as Putri, P. (2023). Knappeit in einer Welt des Überflusses. Wasserkrisen in Indonesien und ihre Ursachen. *Sozialistische Zeitung* Nr. 6 38.Jg. Juni 2023 s. 16; sozonline.de (also available [online](#)).

According to the World Atlas 2018, Indonesia is in the seventh rank of countries with the most renewable fresh water resources, when we omit the European Union as a continental sum with a rank just above Indonesia, following Brazil at the top, Russia, USA, Canada, China and Columbia. Indonesia's area-average total rainfall is in a range from 180 to 280 mm per month throughout the year; as an illustration, compare it with Germany in a range from 35 to 100. Where does the water flow in the archipelago, and who taps the rainwater and benefit from it?

In this article, I do not offer comprehensive statistics or contemporary data of the Indonesian water sector. I rather seek to provide a picture on a big canvas, painted with some critical perspectives. I do hope this would invite engaged communities in different places, to discuss and initiate more radical civil society movements, in whatever roles they might take: scholars-activists, left-lining policy makers, community engineers, farmer associations, or community leaders with their mandates to protect livelihoods. I begin with water in the city, and link it further with the greater problems of urbanization and the capitalist model of modernity. I end by showing some possible, relevant moves to pursue in new critical research agenda.

What Makes Cities: Bodily Dependencies on Commercialized Water

Living in a water-blessed area, the majority of Indonesia's urban populations rely on bottled drinking water. The 2020 official data of BPOM, the national Food and Drug Monitoring Agency, shows that there have been registered 7,780 brands of bottled drinking water, produced by 1.032 firms, in various size and material type of plastic packages. In 2015 alone, they together produced around 25 billion liters and the trend was 12% increase of yearly production since 2009. The French Aqua-Danone is currently the biggest player in the business.

Drinking bottled water is not a lifestyle that one could choose or refuse, it is a necessity. The piped-water company in Jakarta, for example, only serves around 60 per cent of the population with non-drinking-quality water, and even in some low coastal areas, the supply is intermittent due to low water pressure in the pipe networks. An elementary school teacher in Jakarta, one of my long interlocutors in the past eight year of research trajectory, lives alone in a 3x3 m² rental room without own toilet and kitchen in the house. He consumes 100% of his needs for drinking and cooking from non-recyclable plastic bottles. People in his *kampung*, the so-called informal settlement, like in many others, tend to switch to bottled drinking water, from the previous mode of provision that is cooking water from wells

or the tap, following the rise of energy price. During my fieldwork in 2018, I have not noticed such landscape of commercial bottled water in the teacher's kampung. Now it is perceived normal to also see more dumping of plastic bottles, as reported by my fieldwork partners, the young artists of Muara Suara, an art and media collective based in Samarinda and Jakarta.

Our teacher interlocutor, in his room packed with empty water galloons. He re-used them for planting but the use had been insignificant to the speed of consumption.

Source: drawing by Anggraeni Widhiasih and Dini Adanurani, Muara Suara, in their project of 'sketching as a research instrument', in collaboration with CO-Water Research Program, Universität Kassel, with funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101029193.

It might sound that the spending for drinking water shares a little percentage of the monthly income (if one would ever be lucky enough to have a tenured job), but it is in fact still a significant spending while there has been an absence of good welfare system. Spending for drinking water in a household of a teacher with two children can reach to 5 per cent of her or his annual income. The percentage might be less if a household would consume water from water kiosks that are privately run by community entrepreneurs; a water kiosk buys bulk water in trucks from rural providers and the kiosk undergoes local treatment and stores the purified water in locally sterilized used gallons. The quality of the so-called non-branded refilled water has been questionable. Upper middle-class families tend to rely on branded bottled water at home, in the office, in cafes and restaurants. The metropolitan region of Jakarta, in which around 30 million people live, rely on plastic bottles for curing the thirst of its

inhabitants. While the informal sector contributes to around 21 per cent of its Gross Domestic Product (GDP), the informal workers are juggling risks to deal with increasing monthly spending while the income is far from being secured.

Post-colonial Landscape of Dams

The above story should tell us about the structural problem of the infrastructure regime. Jakarta cannot make use of rain water that falls into its own administrative area. The piped water company makes use of Jakarta's river basins only for less than 5 per cent of its total raw water input because the rivers are heavily polluted. For more than 30 years of development, with international debts and scandals of corruption, Jakarta Province has only developed waste water collection network and treatment system that covers only around five per cent of its area. As a result, 82 per cent of raw water resource of the piped-water system has to be channeled from Jatiluhur Dam, some 80 kilometers away in West Java. West Java is a highly fertile region, supposedly feed the people with sufficient agricultural production, but the farmers and peasants have to face water conflicts.

Dam, water reservoir and canal in the Indonesian archipelago have been the modernist symbol of (colonial) progress and prosperity. In Java alone, there are 86 dams built and utilized for irrigation, domestic and industrial clean water supply and electricity generation (according to Public Works and Housing Ministry, 2021). Many policy reports suggest a significant improvement for irrigation by channeling water from these dams, as they now support nearly 720,000 hectares of agriculture lands. Ironically, large dams have been built by taking over community productive lands, while their function to retain water flow destroys community water systems. First, they grab the land, second, the water. Below is an example of the suffocating cycle of dam development, a modernist model to support capitalist urbanization and food system.

Communities of Wadas Village in Central Java have been struggling against stone mining. The extraction is meant to provide materials to build the new dam, Bendungan Bener, that itself will take over 313 hectares of community land. The Dam will be the main water and energy source for the newly built airport in Yogyakarta, the city of universities and tourism. Project Multatuli, a progressive journalistic platform that promotes the spirits of commoning knowledge, has reported in detail the case of Wadas.¹ Productive landscapes with community forests and farming, which yearly produce commodities with the value of nearly 14 billion Indonesian Rupiahs, are at danger. Water security has been modelled at the expense of food security, while the purpose of water provision is to enhance economic growth. Not that far from Wadas, in the Kendeng karst regions in which fresh water is deposited, local communities are fighting against cement industry, on which dam constructions rely on. Cement factories in Java, including the one invested by Heidelberg Cement, have met the highest volume of Indonesia's construction needs. The capacity of production is bigger than the current needs, but new needs is also again and again created. We can think of the gigantic plan of new Indonesian capital region in Borneo, or the under-construction giant sea wall and land reclamations in a Dubai-like Jakarta Bay.

¹ See two reports in <https://projectmultatuli.org/tanah-surga-wadas-dijadikan-tambang-mengapa-pemerintah-menindas-petani/> and <https://projectmultatuli.org/wadon-wadas-menjaga-alam-untuk-anak-cucu/>

Where to start curing the water crises?

Our water crisis is a multiple crisis. It is not about scarcity or mis-managed resource. It is a manifestation of social-environmental injustice. While international organizations have called for transformation in water governance, in a polite tone, they have not loudly said to stop land grab, which has a key role in our water crisis as I have illustrated above. We know very well what has been served by the land that has been stolen from local communities: capitalist industrialization and financialization. It is an important research agenda to trace the links of water and land grab, but also to explain well all related causal mechanisms. This includes the mechanisms that silence people's voice and hindrance stronger social movements. While the global water justice movement has led to the birth of the People's Water Forum, or the opponent of the World Water Forum as the key platform to voice in loud the neoliberal water policy, the water justice movement needs to be supported by more grounded research. While more and more water think-tanks have been working to support the advancement of neoliberal water policies, there have been only weak alternatives on the ground to exercise more socially-and-environmentally just models of water provision and water resource restorations. As I have the legitimation to speak as an academic, critical researchers should participate for the coming People's Water Forum in Bali 2024. Different case studies of academic research across the world should play the role as the bridge of grassroots-to-grassroots exchange and cooperation.